

activity. The most active compounds of the series were 6, 11, 12 and 16 to 18.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur and Dr. Y. B. Singh, Principal, St. Andrew's College, Gorakhpur for providing the necessary facilities.

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Chemical Examination of Essential Oil of *Tagetes minuta* Linn.

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Manuscript received 22 September 1980, accepted
23 February 1981

PLANT—*Tagetes minuta* Linn. (Family Compositae).

Isolation procedure—Steam distillation (Yield 0.8%).

Physical constants—Sp. gravity 0.8731, n_D^{25} 1.5896, $(\alpha)_D^{25} +4.67$, acid value-2.3218, ester value 53.69, ester value after acetylation 134.87 and carbonyl value as $C_{10}H_{16}O$ -27.08%

Previous work—Few workers¹⁻³ have reported the chemistry of essential oil from flowering tops and separated phenolic and non-phenolic terpenes of the oil.

Different constituents of the oil were separated by Kiesel gel column using the solvent benzene-ethyl acetate (95:5). The identified terpenes have been listed in Table 1. Ir spectra were obtained on Perkin-Elmer

TABLE 1

Compounds	Yield	Methods of identification
Aromendrene	23.90	ir. nmr, n_D^{25} 1.4647, Co-TLC, and GLC.
α -Pinene	0.96	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.46627, nopinic acid ⁴ , Co-TLC and GLC.
β -Phellandrene	1.04	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4787, Co-TLC and GLC.
d-Limonene	9.60	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4746, Co-TLC and GLC.
Ocimene	13.10	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4857, Co-TLC and GLC.
β -Myrcene	16.40	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4889, Co-TLC and GLC.
Caryophyllene	0.36	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.
p-Cymene	0.43	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.
Tagetone	15.10	ir, Methyl isobutyl ketone adducts.* Co-TLC and GLC.
d-Carvone	6.10	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.
Linalool	3.60	ir, n_D^{25} -1.4624, Co-TLC and GLC.
Linalylacetate	4.30	ir, n_D^{25} -1.6327, Co-TLC and GLC.
Eugenol	0.47	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.

* All the melting points of derivatives were compared with the melting points given by Guenther.

NOTES

457 and nmr measurements were made on Varian A-60D. The presence of the isolated terpenes was also confirmed by glc which was carried out on gas chromatograph model -900 B equipped with FID detector and UCCW 982 10% 1.8 m column.

Acknowledgement

We are indebted to Prof. H. Wagner, Director, Institut für Pharmazeutische Arzneimittellehre, München (W. Germany) for ir and nmr. Thanks are also due

to UGC for sanctioning the research project to one of us (R.K.B.) under which work could be done.

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